

Change in Food Habits of Urban People and its Impact on Dry Land Farming of Surrounding Rural Areas

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ABSTRACT

Urban areas influences the surrounding areas greatly in all aspects like their living pattern, economic pattern and their rural morphology. The urban food habits will have impact on the rural cultivation pattern. The dry land farming areas surrounding urban centre will have the mutual relationship with the urban region. The dry land farming pattern greatly influenced by the changing food habits in urban region. The dry land farming is necessarily important for the sustainable growth of urban. The respected governments and organizations should be way forward for dry land farming with change in food habits of urban people.

INTRODUCTION

The urban areas are developed since ancient times mostly by their marketing nature. The urban region acted as trading medium and market for the products of rural people. In earlier times the urban food habits are dependent on the cultivating pattern of rural areas as the surrounding region is the sole supplier of ingredients to urban area thanks to low level development of transportation and infrastructure. The consumption of urban people is mainly dry farming products such as millets and pulses. The lack of irrigation facilities also impacted this.

With the agricultural revolution and industrial revolution the urban food habits changed rapidly the food habits are not sole dependent on surrounding region as their options are increased with the infrastructural and agricultural production due. With the industrial revolution the cities are grown rapidly surrounding industrial region and demand for food

increased from other regions with land usage pattern in urban areas changed and land from agricultural practices turned towards industrial purpose. This increased the trading in food items for urban areas and people also changed to more carbohydrates based food from imports rather than the millets and other dry farming products in surrounding areas. This greatly influenced the dry land farming in surround region as their market is lost to other food products.

With the Green revolution in many countries the food production increased rapidly and food habits changed a lot in urban areas and food production in world. With increased irrigation facilities and infrastructure the production of coarse cereals increased rapidly but at same time the millets production and pulses production was not increased that much. This caused the people to go for coarse cereals rather than earlier millets and pulses. This a se back to the dry land farming in many countries in world.

After globalization the food habits of urban people changed greatly due to the free access of markets of countries by foreign companies. Many MNCs are grown in food sector in many countries. People changed their food habits also due to the working conditions in urban areas. The packed food and carbohydrates rich food gain market in all countries. The western impact increased on urban food habits and decreased the demand for local food ingredients especially for dry land farm productions such as millets and pulses etc. The ready available food and chain food markets further intensified the decrease of demand for the surrounding local dry land products.

The recent studies about the millets and their nutritional values once again caused the world again to look for the dry land farming. The negative impacts of green revolution also turned the people to look for alternatives. The organic production is mostly practicing method for good and healthy sustainable production. The organic production can be best practiced in dry land areas as it requires low amount of machines and inputs. The locally available raw materials also used so cost of production also reduces.

The most urban people are suffering from obesity mainly due to changed food habits such as shift from fibre content rich products to readily available carbohydrates and protein rich food items. Shifting of people from energy rich food to fibre rich food also increases the livelihood conditions of people living in surrounding areas. The micro nutrients present in millets also push the urban people to go for the rural bound production food. Due to globalization impact the dry land farming across the world will be increased due to change in urban food habits. The cost of production of dry land goods also low, it may also push people to go for it.

CONCLUSION

The governments and international organizations must step forward in this way to encourage the dry land farming to increase the livelihood of rural people and also help urban people to attain high health standards. The main drawback is low productivity of dry land farming. The institutions should increase research in this way to improve the productivity of millets and other dry land products to meet the demands in future. This also helps for improvement in sustainable development in agriculture and also the barren lands in rural areas will also come into cultivation. This can improve the food security in urban areas and also increases the rural livelihood standards.